

FARMERS AND DEALERS ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE USE OF ORGANIC PESTICIDES IN WASHIM DISTRICT WITH

SPECIAL REFERENCE TO SARDAR AGRI CHEMICAL Pvt. Ltd.

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Abstract

This study investigates the perceptions of farmers and dealers towards organic pesticides in Washim district of Maharashtra, with special reference to Sardar Agri Chemical Pvt. Ltd. Organic pesticides, derived from natural sources such as plants, minerals, and microbes, are considered eco-friendly alternatives to chemical pesticides. They promote sustainable agriculture by reducing chemical residues, preserving soil health, and ensuring safer produce. A total of 60 farmers and 15 dealers were selected from different talukas of the district for the study. Washim district was purposively chosen based on the prevalence of organic pesticide use among farmers and its distribution by local dealers.

The findings revealed that farmers who adopted organic pesticides observed improvements in soil health, crop quality, and long-term productivity. Most farmers had basic to higher education levels, which contributed to their openness towards organic farming practices. Dealers were generally aware of the benefits of organic pesticides and expressed a positive attitude towards their sale, especially due to increasing farmer demand and profit margins. However, key concerns such as higher prices, limited awareness, and occasional availability issues were noted. Despite these challenges, both farmers and dealers recognized the growing importance of organic pesticides. This study highlights their advantages, identifies constraints in adoption, and suggests strategies for improving awareness, availability, and marketing of organic pesticides in the region.

Keywords: Farmers, dealers, organic pesticide, chemical pesticide, perception, attitude, level of knowledge, strategies.

Introduction and Objectives

The growing concerns about the negative impact of conventional chemical pesticides on the environment, public health, and long-term agricultural sustainability have spurred interest in organic alternatives. Organic pesticides, derived from natural sources, offer a safer, more sustainable way to manage pest populations while reducing the detrimental effects associated with synthetic chemicals. With increasing consumer demand for organic food and a growing awareness of the ecological consequences of chemical pesticide use, organic pesticides have become a significant component of modern integrated pest management (IPM) strategies.

Organic pesticides are primarily derived from natural substances like plants, animals, microorganisms, or minerals. These substances are either naturally occurring or processed in such a way that they have minimal impact on the environment and non-target species. The primary aim of organic pesticides is to control pests without posing the risks that are associated with chemical pesticides, such as contamination of soil, water, and air, as well as toxicity to humans and wildlife. The global organic pesticide market was valued at USD 6.3 billion in 2021, and is projected to grow at a CAGR of 9.5% from 2022 to 2030. In contrast, chemical pesticides dominate with 99% market share, while organic pesticides account for only 1%, though this figure is growing.

Organic farming principles emphasize sustainability and the avoidance of synthetic chemicals. Organic pesticides align with these principles, supporting the use of natural substances and methods that maintain ecological balance, protect biodiversity, and promote soil and water health. Organic pesticides are often used in combination with other techniques such as crop rotation, biological pest control, and habitat management to minimize pest pressure without harming beneficial organisms.

The specific objectives of the study are:

- 1) To study the market share of organic product produced by Sardar Agri Chemicals
- 2) To study the farmers level of knowledge and attitude towards the use of organic pesticide.
- 3) To study the factor associated with purchase of organic pesticide by farmers

- 4) To assess dealers preference towards the selling of organic pesticides.
- 5) To suggest strategies for the marketing of organic pesticides in the study area.

Methodology**Study area**

The present study was conducted in Washim district of Maharashtra during the academic year 2024–25. This district was purposively selected due to the increasing number of farmers using organic pesticides and the presence of various dealers actively engaged in selling these products, particularly those affiliated with Sardar Agri Chemical Pvt. Ltd. The research aimed to understand the attitudes of farmers and dealers towards organic pesticide usage in the region. For data collection, a survey method was employed, involving personal interviews with both farmers and dealers. Three talukas Karanja Lad, Mangrulpir, and Washim were selected for the study. From each of these talukas, two villages were chosen, and 10 farmers were selected from each village, resulting in a total sample of 60 farmers. The selected villages included Karanja Lad and Amgavan from Karanja Lad taluka; Wae and Dhotra from Mangrulpir taluka; and Tandali and Walhae from Washim taluka.

In addition to the farmers, 15 dealers were also selected for the study 5 from each of the three talukas to gain insights into their knowledge, preferences, and promotional practices related to organic pesticides. This sampling approach ensured a diverse and representative set of responses from across the district.

Analysis of data:

A simple tabular analysis was carried out to study the socio-economic attributes of the selected farmers, examine the factors influencing the purchase of organic pesticides, and assess the farmers' level of knowledge and attitude towards the use of organic pesticides in Washim district. The analysis also aimed to evaluate the dealers' preferences for selling organic pesticides, determine the market share of organic pesticides in the study area, and identify effective marketing strategies for their promotion. To interpret the data efficiently and present meaningful results, statistical tools such as percentages were used, ensuring clear and comprehensive insights across all study objectives.

Results and Discussion**Market Share of Organic Pesticide in Washim District**

Sale of Organic Pesticide in Washim District 2024-2025

Table. 1 presents the sale of organic pesticides in Washim district for the year 2024–2025, highlighting the performance of five major brands. The total quantity of organic pesticides sold during this period was 73,495 litres. Among the brands, Sardar Agri Chemicals recorded the highest sales with 16,126 litres, accounting for 21.94% of the total market share. This indicates a strong presence and acceptance of the brand among farmers in the region, possibly due to effective marketing strategies, product performance, or dealer support. Following closely is TATA, with 15,470 litres sold, contributing 21.05% to the total sales. Aushadh and IFC also secured significant portions of the market, with 19.84% and 19.51% respectively. Kay Bee, although slightly behind, maintained a competitive share of 17.66%. The distribution of sales among the five brands suggests a competitive market environment where no single brand holds an overwhelming majority, but Sardar Agri Chemicals leads slightly, reflecting its growing influence and trust among users in Washim district.

Socioeconomic Attributes of Selected Farmers

Table. 2 shows socio-economic profile of the 60 farmers surveyed in Washim district reveals several key characteristics. In terms of landholding, a majority of farmers (28 farmers or 46%) fall into the small category with holdings up to 2 hectares, followed by 22 farmers (37%) with medium holdings between 2.01 to 4 hectares, and only 10 farmers (17%) possessing large farms above 4 hectares. Age-wise, the farming community is predominantly middle-aged, with 37 farmers (61%) between 36 to 55 years, while 16 farmers (27%) are below 35 years, and only 7 farmers (12%) are above 55 years. Educationally, the data shows a relatively well-educated group, with 25 farmers (42%) being graduates and 13 farmers (22%) postgraduates. The remaining include 11 farmers (18%) with higher secondary education, 4 farmers (6%) who completed SSC, and 7 farmers (12%) who are illiterate.

Family structure analysis indicates that 38 farmers (63%) belong to medium-sized families with 5 to 6 members, followed by 12 farmers (20%) from large families and 10 farmers (17%) from small families. Notably, a large proportion of the respondents (48 farmers or 80%) live in nuclear families, while only 12 farmers (20%) belong to joint families, reflecting a shift toward modern family setups. Regarding income, 20 farmers (33%) have an annual income up to ₹1,00,000, 15 farmers (25%) fall in the ₹1,00,001–₹3,00,000 bracket, 18 farmers (30%) earn between ₹3,00,001 and ₹6,00,000, and only 7 farmers (12%) earn above ₹6,00,000 annually. In terms of occupation, 31 farmers (52%) depend solely on agriculture, while 21 farmers (35%) combine farming with service-based jobs and 8 farmers (13%) run shops alongside agriculture. This data indicates a diversified livelihood strategy among farmers, with a substantial number balancing multiple income sources to sustain their households.

Farmers Level of Knowledge and Attributes Towards Use of Organic Pesticide in Washim District.**Distribution of Farmers on the Basis of Source of Information**

The data from Table. 3 regarding the sources of information about organic pesticides among the 60 surveyed farmers in Washim district reveals varied channels of awareness. Social media emerged as the most commonly used source, with 16 farmers (27%) relying on platforms such as WhatsApp, YouTube, or Facebook to gain information related to organic pesticides. This highlights the increasing influence of digital communication even in rural agricultural communities. Krushi Seva Kendra, the agricultural input shops and service centers, served as a primary source for 15 farmers (25%), indicating the trust farmers place in these centers for technical guidance and product knowledge.

An equal number of farmers (15 farmers or 25%) also cited demonstrations as an effective source of information. Neighbouring farmers influenced the decisions of 9 respondents (15%), which reflects

the traditional method of knowledge transfer through peer experience and word-of-mouth. Lastly, 5 farmers (8%) reported that banners and posters served as a source of information, indicating that while print-based marketing has limited reach, it still plays a role in spreading awareness.

Factors Associated with Purchase of Organic Pesticide by Farmers in Washim District**Factors associated with purchase of organic pesticide in terms of price, dealers perception, brand reputation**

Table. 4 shows data collected from 60 farmers highlights several key factors influencing the purchase of organic pesticides in Washim district. When it comes to price, a majority of farmers (32 farmers or 53%) preferred products priced at a medium level, indicating a balance between cost and perceived value. 22 farmers (37%) reported purchasing high-priced organic pesticides, likely reflecting their belief in better quality or effectiveness, while only 6 farmers (10%) opted for low-priced products, suggesting that price alone is not the primary deciding factor. In terms of dealers' perception, 34 farmers (57%) noted that the organic pesticides they purchased had a good sale record, showing strong market acceptance and confidence in the product's performance. The remaining 26 farmers (43%) mentioned average sale, indicating moderate market presence. Similarly, brand reputation played a significant role, with 34 farmers (57%) favoring brands with a good reputation, while 26 farmers (43%) chose products with average reputation. This reflects that both the dealer's endorsement and brand image are important considerations for farmers when deciding which organic pesticide to purchase.

Factors associated with purchase of organic pesticide in terms of timely availability, cost saving & result

Table. 5 represents data from 60 farmers in Washim district reveals key factors influencing their preference for organic pesticides. Timely availability was affirmed by 33 farmers (55%), indicating that more than half were able to access organic pesticides when needed, while 27 farmers (45%) faced delays or unavailability, which could affect adoption rates. In terms of cost saving, 36 farmers (60%) reported that using organic pesticides helped reduce overall expenses, possibly through lower input costs or fewer applications. Conversely, 24 farmers (40%) did not perceive any significant cost advantage. Regarding effectiveness, 36 farmers (60%) observed positive results from using organic pesticides on their crops, whereas 24 farmers (40%) did not find them as effective.

Dealers Preference Towards the Selling of Organic Pesticide in Washim District**Perception of Dealers in Terms of Sale and Result of Organic Pesticide and Chemical Pesticide**

Data from Table. 6 shows 15 dealers across Karanja Lad, Manglurpir, and Washim talukas shows that 10 prefer selling organic pesticides, while 5 favor chemical ones. Karanja Lad had more dealers preferring chemical pesticides (3 vs. 2), while Manglurpir and Washim leaned toward organic options (4 each vs. 1 for chemical). Regarding effectiveness, 9 dealers found organic pesticides more effective, compared to 6 for chemical pesticides. In Karanja Lad, 4 saw better results with organic pesticides. However, in Manglurpir, chemical pesticides were considered more effective by 3 dealers. Washim again showed a slight preference for organic results. Overall, the trend reflects a positive shift toward organic pesticides in terms of both preference and effectiveness, especially in Washim and Manglurpir.

Strategies for the Marketing of Organic Pesticide in Washim District Types of marketing strategies most effective in convincing to use organic pesticides

Table. 7 represents data highlights the various marketing strategies adopted by dealers to promote organic pesticides. Among the 15 dealers surveyed, the most commonly used strategy was providing information through local retail stores, reported by 5 dealers (33.33%). This suggests that retail outlets play a key role in influencing farmers' purchasing

decisions. Local advertisements were the next most popular method, used by 4 dealers (26.66%), indicating the importance of traditional media in spreading awareness. Other strategies such as direct marketing through agricultural extension services, social media campaigns, and product demonstrations were each employed by 2 dealers (13.33%). These figures show that while modern tools like social media and direct outreach are being used, traditional and retail-based methods remain the primary marketing channels in the region.

5. Conclusion

The study carried out in Washim district during 2024–2025 offers valuable insights into the attitudes and preferences of both farmers and dealers regarding organic pesticides, with a specific emphasis on products from Sardar Agri Chemicals Pvt. Ltd. The results reveal a growing acceptance of organic pesticides among farmers, with 60% finding them more effective than chemical alternatives and equally appreciating their ease of use.

Although concerns about cost and availability persist, most farmers viewed the pricing as reasonable and were satisfied with the results. Trust in well-known brands and a strong preference among middle-aged, educated farmers from joint families highlight a supportive environment for organic solutions. Additionally, small and medium landholders who make up the majority of the farming community show a strong inclination toward sustainable pest control, positioning them as a key audience for future marketing efforts.

Dealers also showed a generally positive outlook, with 60% considering organic pesticides economically viable and 53% agreeing that prices and availability were acceptable. Out of 15 dealers, 10 preferred selling organic over chemical pesticides, particularly in Mangrulpir and Washim talukas, indicating regional differences in market trends.

Regarding promotional methods, traditional approaches like retail store outreach and local advertising remain dominant. However, modern marketing tools such as social media, demonstrations, and agricultural extension services are gaining traction. Most dealers favored off-season promotions as a strategy to raise awareness and educate farmers before high-demand periods.

In summary, the Washim district demonstrates a strong and growing inclination toward organic pesticide adoption, supported by both farmers and dealers. To enhance and sustain this momentum, efforts should focus on improving affordability, ensuring a steady supply, raising awareness, and strengthening dealer-farmer engagement. Such targeted strategies can help advance the organic pesticide market and support more environmentally friendly farming practices in the region.

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Table 1. Sale of Organic Pesticide in Washim District 2024-2025

Sr. No	Brand Name	Qty sale (Ltr)	Percentage
1	TATA	15470	21.05
2	IFC	14340	19.51
3	Kay Bee	12980	17.66
4	Aushadh	14579	19.84
5	Sardar Agri Chemicals	16126	21.94
Total		73495	100.00

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table. 2: Socioeconomic Attributes of Selected Farmers

Sr. No.	Factors	No of Farmers (n=60)
1.	Landholding	
	Small (Upto 2 Ha.)	28 (46.00)
	Medium (2.01 to 4Ha.)	22 (37.00)
	Large (Above 4 Ha.)	10 (17.00)
2.	Age	
1	Young (Upto 35)	16 (27.00)
2	Middle Age (36-55)	37 (61.00)
3	Old (Above 55)	7 (12.00)
3.	Education	
	Illiterate	7 (12.00)
	SSC	4 (6.00)
	HSC	11 (18.00)
	Graduate	25 (42.00)
	Post Graduate	13 (22.00)
4.	Family Size	
	Small (Upto 4)	10 (17.00)
	Medium (5-6)	38 (63.00)
	Large (More than 6)	12 (20.00)
5.	Type of Family	
	Nuclear family	48 (80.00)
	Joint family	12 (20.00)
6.	Annual Income	
	Upto 100000	20 (33.00)
	100001-300000	5 (25.00)
	300001-600000	18 (30.00)
	600001 and above	7 (12.00)
7.	Occupation (Main & Sub)	
	Agriculture	31 (52.00)

	Agriculture	Shop	8 (13.00)
	Agriculture	Service	21 (35.00)

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table. 3: Farmers Level of Knowledge and Attributes Towards Use of Organic Pesticide in Washim District

Sr. No.	Source of Information	No of Farmers (n=100)	Percentage
1	Krushi Seva Kendra	15	25.00
2	Neighbouring Farmer	9	15.00
3	Social media	16	27.00
4	Demonstration	15	25.00
5	Banner	5	8.00
	Total	60	100.00

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table No. 4 Factors associated with purchase of organic pesticide in terms of price, dealers perception, brand reputation

Sr. No.	Factor	No. of Farmer (n=60)	Percentage
1.	Price		
	Low	6	10.00
	Medium	32	53.00
	High	22	37.00
2.	Dealers Perception		
	Good Sale	34	57.00
	Average Sale	26	43.00
3.	Brand Reputation		
	Good	34	57.00
	Average	26	43.00

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table No. 5: Factors associated with purchase of organic pesticide in terms of timely availability, cost saving & result

Sr. No.	Factors	No. of Farmer (n=60)	Percentage
1.	Timely Availability		
	Yes	33	55.00
	No	27	45.00
2.	Cost Saving		
	Yes	36	60.00
	No	24	40.00
3.	Result		
	Yes	36	60.00
	No	24	40.00

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)

Table. 6: Perception of Dealers in Terms of Sale and Result of Organic Pesticide and Chemical Pesticide

Sr. No.	Name of Taluka	Dealers Preference Towards sale Organic Pesticide	Dealers Preference Towards sale Chemical Pesticide
1.	Karanja lad	2	3
2.	Manglurpir	4	1
3.	Washim	4	1
Total	(No of Dealer = 15)	10	5
	Name of Taluka	Result of Organic Pesticide	Result of Chemical Pesticide
1.	Karanja lad	4	1
2.	Manglurpir	2	3
3.	Washim	3	2
Total	(No of Dealer = 15)	9	6

Table. 7: Types of marketing strategies most effective in convincing to use organic pesticides

Sr. No	Type of Marketing Strategies	No of Dealers	Percentage
1	Direct marketing through agricultural extension services	2	13.33
2	Social media campaigns	2	13.33
3	Local advertisements	4	26.66
4	Demonstrations	2	13.33
5	Information through local retail stores	5	33.33
Total		15	100.00

(Figure in parenthesis indicate percentage)